

CHARACTERISTICS OF TECHNICAL EQUIPMENT USED IN WEIGHTLIFTING

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Abstract: In this thesis, in addition to the study of the movement parameters of weightlifters, sufficient thought was given to the measurement of muscle strength.

Key words: Weightlifting, sport, technique, tactics, muscle, strength, athlete.

Modern training of weightlifters cannot be imagined without various technical means. Their widespread use makes it possible to significantly increase the effectiveness of the training process in the training of both high-class weightlifters and beginner athletes. There are three characteristics of technical equipment used in the sport of weightlifting.

Various measuring instruments for sports research and practical purposes; all kinds of technical means both for individual muscle groups and for comprehensive physical training; technical tools aimed at studying movement parameters and improving the technique of weightlifting exercises.

The first group. In this group of technical tools, the tools aimed at measuring muscle strength and studying their performance are the most deeply developed. Thus, B.V. Evstafiev, A.S. Sakharov created a special universal dynamometer to study athletes' resistance to force and static tension. This dynamograph consists of the following parts: scales (a dial indicator, an intermediate mechanism and a platform that perceives movements); a solid platform and neck racks, through which the athlete's efforts are transmitted to the mechanism of perception of the scales.

To determine the performance of a number of muscle groups, V.B. Airepetyan, R.Ya. Juganyan, F.G. Kazarian, M.A. Kesednyan designed and implemented the dynamographic setup. This setup allows an in-depth study of the dynamic and static

performance of individual muscle groups of athletes, specifically recording the strength of the flexors and extensors of the arm, wrist, torso, hip, lower leg, and foot. The installation includes the following main parts: a table for setting the subject in the desired position, a system of blocks with a dynamometer for determining the maximum strength of individual muscle groups, a system of blocks with a cart for studying muscle performance. dynamic and static work, attachment to the table (table) for the work of the hand and wrist, pedal for the work of the foot; tape recorders recording the dynamic and static work of muscles; speedometer.

A very original device for measuring strength, height and body weight V.T. Chichikin. This device allows you to determine the maximum static strength, strength and static endurance, the accuracy of increasing the strength of the following muscle groups: forearm, thigh, lower leg, trunk, leg in flexion-extension movements, as well as growth and weight. indicators. In addition, the device can be used to develop flexibility. The device consists of a frame, a system of blocks and a writing mechanism.

A high level of sports results requires the athletes to have a high level of physical fitness, as well as the perfect mastering of reasonable movement techniques. Therefore, the problem of improving technical skills in sports training is urgent.

In the chapter “Techniques of performing classical exercises”, modern ideas about technical skills in classical and special training exercises are highlighted. As practice shows, the execution of any special auxiliary exercise should correspond to the coordination mode of lifting and swinging. Otherwise, the effectiveness of training will decrease.

To study the maximum static movements at different moments of the athlete's movement while performing weightlifting exercises. Pletnev and N.I. Luchkin designed a device consisting of a tubular U-shaped frame 2000 mm high and 1250 mm wide, a wooden platform and dynamometers. This device can be used as a means of training muscle strength in isometric mode. G.P. Semenov proposed a technique

for studying muscle work in three modes. The device consists of a double frame, footrests mounted on a moving cart, a special seat, removable handles and a pulley system, and a cable.

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